

Teaching Programming in Primary Schools in Morocco

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Computer science, code, programming, or even computational thinking are some of the terms recently used from elementary school to high school to accompany the arrival of a new discipline that sees its initiation planned from elementary school (MEN, 2015). Designed to introduce children and teenagers to programming, Scratch is a software program that helps children develop programming skills and learn the skills underlying computer thinking.

This paper presents the results of a survey sent to teachers and students in Morocco. The goal of the survey was to find out the opinion of Moroccan people toward programming teaching in Primary Education. 114 respondents filled and returned the survey showing that: 85.1% (51.8% strongly agree, 33.3% agree) out of the respondents consider that teaching programming in Primary Education is functional. Moreover, 71.9% out of 51 respondents use Scratch as specialized software for introducing programming in primary schools.

Keywords: PROGRAMMING, SCRATCH, PRIMARY SCHOOLS, COMPUTER THINKING, COMPUTER SCIENCE.

Introduction

In a world where digital technology has invaded all areas of the economy and society, everyone must be armed with technological skills to cope with hyper-technology daily life. Therefore, the school has a fundamental role in successfully integrating citizens into the economy and the knowledge society. In this perspective, computer science teaching is positioned as a fundamental component to achieve this goal.

Programming education is a sub-field of computer science, and while primarily conducted to educate learners in the best practices of computer programming, one of its goals is to create high-quality computer programs. While it has considerable overlap with computer science on certain elements, computational thinking focuses mainly on developing and disseminating approaches to problem-solving, unlike computer science.

In recent years there has been a movement to promote the teaching of programming in schools worldwide.

Some researchers in the educational and academic community have become interested in the benefits a child can gain from learning to code, regardless of his or her future career field.

In recent years, new programming languages have been designed to be visually programmed without learning syntax, as with traditional languages. Languages such as Alice, Kodu, and especially Scratch have revived the educational community's interest in programming. In addition, the Scratch team has learned from previous experiences to develop a language that allows the creation of many different types of projects so that students with different interests and learning styles can express themselves through programming [1].

Literature review

Constructivist learning theory combined with computer programming was an area of great interest in education in the 1970s and 1980's, but this interest began to wane starting in the 1990's (Lye & Koh, 2014). In contemporary educational contexts, the creation of easy-to-use visual programming languages that have been designed with young students in mind has reinvigorated the idea of using computer programming as a pedagogical tool to develop computational thinking skills. Advocates are calling for computational thinking and computer programming to have a place in school curricula (Grover & Pea, 2013; I. Lee, Martin, & Apone, 2014; Lye & Koh, 2014). Continued research has been called for on the development of computational thinking and the implementation of computer programming across curriculum areas in order to better understand how learners develop their understanding of curricular concepts and computational thinking skills (Grover & Pea, 2013).

➤ Teaching programming in primary schools in Morocco

Morocco has been committed since the 1980s in its educational policy to introduce computer education through several initiatives. However, from the year 2000, with the advent of the national charter of education and training, which insists in the space entitled "Improving the quality of education and training" on the capital place of the use of new information technologies and communication (lever 10), that the teaching of computer science has begun to take its place in the educational system [2]. Thus, computer science as a school subject, at the same level as the other subjects, with a precise hourly volume and well-defined objectives, appeared in the curricular architecture of the Moroccan secondary education curriculum (college and qualifying) [3,4].

In its strategic vision 2015-2030 developed from the recommendations of the framework law No. 51-17 on the system of education, teaching, training and scientific research [5] and especially the lever 20 entitled "Active involvement in the economy and knowledge society", which considers that information technology and communication as an entry into the site of effective membership in the economy and knowledge society, the Ministry of National Education through the direction of the Program GENIE has developed a draft curriculum of computer science that should be taught to student's elementary school students [6]. This program, which is based on the teaching of computer thinking [7] through the use of SCRATCH software aims at developing skills related to problem solving related to problem solving, algorithms, logic and abstraction through exercises or exercises or projects involving other disciplines and, possibly, taking advantage of the opportunity to introduce

students to other aspects (how computers work, etc.).

➤ **Mainland China**

Computer science has been used in the national education system since the 1980s (Mok and Leung 2012). According to Niemi and Jia (2016), the growing popularity of the Internet and communication technologies from the 1990s onwards gave rise to a broader concept of ICT, which was then introduced into general education (Niemi and Jia 2016, p. 9). In 2010, a national education reform and development plan was issued by the central government. It stated that ICT will have a revolutionary impact on education (Ministry of Education of China 2010). Since then, public spending on education has been steadily increasing, and the central and provincial governments have invested heavily in the application of ICT to education (Niemi and Jia 2016, p. 9; Han and Ye 2017).

In 2016, the National People's Congress approved the 13th Five-Year Plan for National Economic and Social Development, which emphasized the importance of improving the educational level of the entire population and promoting the modernization of education. Concrete approaches detailed in this plan include the development of online education and distance learning, the integration of all kinds of digital resources and their service to society as a whole, and the deep integration of ICT with teaching and learning (National People's Congress of China 2016). According to Jia and Niemi (2016, p. 315), "The integration of ICT into ordinary teaching and learning is to cultivate basic knowledge, skills, and literacy in the information age, [...] workplace."

A new high school curriculum reform program was announced in 2016 and implemented starting in 2017, which makes CT one of the four core elements of the information technology discipline. This decision indicates that information technology has been given greater emphasis at the national curriculum level, which will influence the promulgation of new curriculum standards, the composition of new instructional materials, and the direction of new college entrance exams.

➤ **Teaching programming in primary schools in other countries**

Education systems around the world, such as Australia, New Zealand, United States, United Kingdom, South Korea, Finland, and Singapore, have recognized the importance of coding. They are taking rapid measures to introduce it through all levels of the school curriculum. Finland and Singapore have to date revised national standards and curriculum to focus learning goals on higher-order thinking, inquiry, and innovation, as well as the integration of technology to the curriculum. In these systems, the need for educating students in twenty first century skills are commonly acknowledged, which have also been top performers in PISA rankings.

About Scratch

➤ **Definition**

Scratch: is a visual programming environment that lets users create interactive, media-rich projects as shown in the fig. 1. People have created a wide range of projects with Scratch, including animated stories, games, online news shows, book reports, greeting cards, music videos, science projects, tutorials, simulations, and sensor-driven art and music projects

Figure 1: screenshot of scratch interface.

➤ The history of Scratch

The original design of Scratch was motivated by the needs and interests of young people (ages 8 to 16) at after-school computer centres such as the Intel Computer Clubhouses (Resnick et al. 2003). Scratch added programmability to media-manipulation activities that are popular in youth culture, and it encouraged young people to learn through exploration and peer sharing, with less focus on direct instruction than other programming languages. Initially, Scratch was used primarily in informal learning settings such as community centres, after-school clubs, libraries, and homes, but increasingly it is used in schools as well.

The Scratch project began in 2003, and the Scratch software and Web site were publicly launched in 2007. Scratch is free, available in nearly 50 languages, and more than two million copies have been downloaded from the Scratch Web site. In addition, Scratch software is often redistributed by school systems and educational organizations.

Scratch builds on the constructionist ideas of Logo [Kafai and Resnick 1996; Papert 1980] and Etoys [Kay 2010; Steinmetz 2002]. To help users make their projects personally engaging, motivating, and meaningful, Scratch makes it easy to import or create many kinds of media (images, sounds, music). The Scratch Web site provides a social context for Scratch users, allowing users to share their Scratch projects, receive feedback and encouragement from their peers, and learn from the projects of others [Resnick et al. 2009].

➤ The goal of Scratch

A key goal of Scratch is to introduce programming to those with no previous programming experience. This goal drove many aspects of the Scratch design. Some of the design decisions are obvious, such as the choice of a visual block's language, the single-window user interface layout, and the minimal command set. Others are less obvious, such as how the target audience influenced the type system and the approach to error handling. [8]

Materials and methods

Programming and robotics are relatively new fields. Programming refers to what used to be called "logistical thinking", now called "computational thinking" in reference to "computational reason" (É. Bruillard,

2012b). This case study seeks to describe how Moroccan students and teachers think toward teaching programming in primary schools.

The survey is designed to address three major guiding questions:

1. What are the perceptions of the new Moroccan generation on programming in general?
2. What is their opinion on teaching programming in primary schools?
3. What are their perceptions towards teaching programming skills by using SCRATCH 3?

Participants

The sample subject of the survey consists of Moroccan teachers and students of different educational levels.

- The first section of the questionnaire includes questions about computer science and programming background.
- The 2nd and 3rd sections include questions about their opinion regarding teaching programming in primary schools by using scratch 3.

Results

The questionnaire was answered by 150 respondents, 36 responses were cancelled because they were not serious. Therefore, 114 responses will be analysed and discussed in this study.

The responses were like this:

- Question 4: what is your gender?

Out of 114 respondents, 52.6% are males and 47.4% are females.

- Question 2: what is your educational degree?

59.6% out of 114 respondents are postgraduate, 30.7% are undergraduate, 9.7% are holders of bachelor, baccalaureate...

➤ **Question 3: Do you have any background knowledge about programming?**

58.8% Out of 114 respondents have background knowledge about programming, 41.2% have no background knowledge.

➤ **Question 4: have you studied programming before?**

58.8% out of 114 respondents have not studied programming before, 41.2% have studied programming before.

➤ **Question 5: would you be interested in studying programming?**

84.2% out of 114 respondents are interested in studying programming, 15.8% are not interested in studying programming.

➤ **Question 6: Do you think programming has an important role in student's career?**

93.9% out of 114 respondents think programming has an important role in student's career, 6.1% think programming has no important role in student's career

➤ Question 7: Do you agree that kids should start learning programming from primary school?

Out of 114 responses:

- 51.8% strongly agree
- 33.3% agree
- 13.2 neutral
- 1.8% disagree

➤ Question 8: which year of primary school do you think is suitable to start studying programming?

- 114 responses:
- 35.1% 6th year
- 25.4% 4th year
- 24.6% 5th year
- 14.9% 3rd year

➤ Question 9: if you have children, would you agree to let them start studying programming from primary school?

Out of 114 responses:

- 57.9% strongly agree
- 31.6% agree
- 7% disagree

3.5 disagree

➤ Question 10: in the context of the parallel activities, could you rank these activities from the most important (number 1) to the least (number 4)?

114 responses.

Programming ranked the second one after sport as the first most important activity, the third one as the second and the third most important activity, and the first one as the least important activity.

➤ Question 11: how many programming languages do you know?

Out of 114 respondents 22.8% know 1 programming language, 22.8% know 2 programming languages, 21.1% know more than 3 programming languages, 21.1% they don't know any programming language and 12.3% know 3 programming languages.

➤ Question 12: Scratch 3 is a programming language software specially designed for kids; do you have any idea about it?

Out of 114 responses 69,3% answered no, 30,7% answered yes

➤ Question 13: if yes, is it a good software to start learning programming in primary schools?
Out of 57 respondents 71.9% answered yes, 17.5% answered no, 10.6 they don't have any idea about it.

➤ Question 14: how many programming classes do you think kids should have every week?
56.1% out of 114 respondents think kids should have two classes per week, 32.1% one classes per week, 11,4% three classes per week.

➤ Question 15: in your opinion, what should be the programming course ratio for theoretical and practical learning?

Out of 114 responses:

63.2% think the ratio should be 40% for theoretical learning and 60% for practical learning.

29.8% think the ratio should be 50% for theoretical learning and 50% for practical learning

7% think the ratio should be 60% for theoretical learning and 40% for practical learning

Discussion of results

Integration of ICT in education is critical for modernizing the traditional teaching-learning structure. Every
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country is racing to make its land a computerized cave because it knows that the technological environment positively impacts learners' performance, to say the least, if good use is made of it. Students' success in all subjects improves when exposed to a technologically enhanced environment (Look, 2005).

Several findings emerge from the questionnaire's responses; the data shows that most of the respondents are into teaching programming in primary schools in Morocco.

From the 3rd question to the sixth one, the programming questions were open and general. The goal is to know the programming background of the respondents. The responses show that most respondents already had background knowledge even though they did not have any background studies. Moreover, the majority think that programming is functional and essential in the student's career. So, we can sum up that teaching programming in schools in general for Moroccan people is an urgent need, especially in this world where digital technology has invaded all economies and society. The world also needs programmers because of the fast growth of computing. It seems likely that the need for programmers will grow in the future. Also, even if the aim is not to become a programmer, knowing how to program will be beneficial because of the number of devices and software. Learning programming skills teach us to use devices and software flexibly. (Boyder et al., 2008; Duncan et al., 2014; Rushkoff, 2010.)

From the 7th question to the 10th one, the questions were about teaching programming in primary schools. The goal is to know the respondents' opinions about teaching programming in primary schools. The results show that the majority strongly agrees with it. Furthermore, three parallel activities besides programming were chosen in the 10th question for comparison. The goal is to know how programming is essential besides the three activities. Programming ranked the second one as the first most crucial activity. In addition, learning programming motivates children to develop their logical thinking. In the literature, the findings of Clements & Nastasi (1999); Fessakis, Gouli, and Mavroudi (2013); Duncan, Bell, and Tanimoto (2014) and Kalelioglu (2015), are supporting the idea that logical and critical thinking is evolved through the development of better problem-solving skills of children, moreover through the development of cognitive and metacognitive skills.

The 11th, 12th, and 13th questions show that most of the respondents know one programming language, and the majority did not have any Idea about scratch 3. Moreover, the plurality of those who had an idea about it agreed that scratch is good software for introducing programming in primary schools.

In the last two questions, the majority think two programming classes per week are more convenient in primary school. Furthermore, most of them think that the ratio of programming classes should be 60% for practical learning and 40% for theoretical learning.

Conclusion

Our survey results showed an acceptable level of satisfaction about teaching programming in primary schools in Morocco. Moreover, the respondents use Scratch as specialized software to introduce programming in primary schools. Furthermore, our study showed that the 6th year of primary school is the best year to start teaching programming; Scratch into the Fundamentals of Programming classes would positively contribute to

student performance. It also allows students to develop the concepts of programming logic and the use of specific basic control structures. In addition, by learning the basics of programming, students will be more interested in learning how to program robots, learn about artificial intelligence, and engage in other exciting projects.

We are aware that this is just a first step towards improving the learning of programming with Scratch in primary schools in Morocco. Introducing computer programs to children can be a challenge, especially for those unfamiliar with the nuances of code. For future work, we will continue our studies. The next step is scratch course design and development; therefore, we need to study and discuss intensely the curriculum in Morocco, teacher's training, the methodology, the design of the course, and the problems that can be faced while integrating programming in primary schools' curriculum in Morocco. Accordingly, we have planned to design a new questionnaire that will consist only of students and teachers who already have studied programming so that it will be more helpful for us to find a suitable programming curriculum for primary schools in Morocco.

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